

1 **Rock diversity drives river network reorganization with** 2 **implications for biotic diversification in continent interiors**

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11

12 ***Summary Paragraph***

13 River captures and drainage divide migration are dynamic processes of river basin reorganization
14 widely observed in tectonically quiescent continent interiors. Because the frequency and
15 magnitude of river-capture events may influence hydrographic connectivity through time, they
16 have important implications for landscape evolution and continental biogeography. Despite these
17 broad implications, a general process capable of explaining the initiation, spatial patterns, and
18 magnitudes of drainage reorganization in tectonically quiescent settings has remained elusive.
19 Here we show that the exhumation of resistant rocks can trigger widespread drainage divide
20 motion and precondition landscapes to river capture, including in areas far upstream of the
21 lithologic contrast, without requiring changes in tectonic or climatic forcing. Because long-term
22 erosion progressively exhumes contrasting rock types, this mechanism provides a persistent
23 internal driver of repeated drainage reorganization through geologic time. We document this
24 mechanism using topographic analyses from landscapes in South and North America and
25 numerical landscape-evolution models. The models show that lithologic contrasts systematically
26 regulate the size, timing, and spatial distribution of river captures across scales. Comparison with
27 published lineage-split ages linked to the positions of rivers in Amazonia further suggests that the
28 timescales of these geomorphic processes are relevant to questions in continental biogeography.
29 Together, these results identify a geomorphic mechanism for recurring drainage reorganization in

30 tectonically quiescent landscapes and provide a geomorphic framework for generating testable
31 hypotheses about links between geodiversity, hydrographic connectivity, and biodiversity.

32

33 ***Significance***

34 Determining how often and by how much river captures reorganize drainage networks is
35 important for understanding landscape evolution and continental biogeography. However, the
36 geologic conditions that govern the timing, spatial distribution, and magnitude of river captures
37 remain poorly constrained. Here we show, using observations from South and North America
38 and numerical landscape evolution models, that the exhumation of contrasting rock types can
39 systematically generate predictable patterns of drainage reorganization by perturbing base-level
40 across neighboring basins. Because erosion continually exposes lithologic contrasts through
41 time, this process provides a persistent internal mechanism for repeated drainage reorganizations.
42 These results identify a geomorphic explanation for widespread drainage reorganization in
43 tectonically quiescent settings and provide a basis for testing how such reorganizations may
44 influence biogeography.

45

46 ***Main text***

47 The slow erosion rates and low relief of tectonically inactive regions have long
48 contributed to the view that such landscapes have little geomorphic activity. However,
49 tectonically quiescent continent interiors such as the eastern Guiana Shield display widespread
50 short-wavelength transient topographic features (Fig. 1) similar to those observed in other
51 geologic and climatic settings (1–4), including southeast Brazil and the western United States
52 (Figs. S1–S4). Various geodynamic, tectonic, and climatic mechanisms have been invoked to
53 explain some of these features in well-constrained settings (5–7). Yet explaining each occurrence
54 through a distinct external trigger requires a separate spatiotemporal history of tectonic or
55 climatic forcing and therefore does not provide a general explanation for widespread landscape
56 transience in tectonically quiescent settings.

57 Spatiotemporal changes in the geologic substrate over which landscapes evolve offer a
58 promising alternative explanation for why drainage networks reorganize repeatedly over tens of
59 millions of years (8). Because some rock types resist erosion more than others, lithologic
60 contrasts near drainage divides can generate differential erosion between adjacent basins, driving

61 divide migration (the continuous movement of a drainage divide between basins), river capture
62 (the rerouting of a river into another basin driven by erosion of the divide separating them), and
63 large-scale drainage reorganization (the broad reconfiguration of river networks and basin
64 connectivity) (1). Yet many transient topographic features are not spatially coincident with the
65 rock contact that ultimately triggers them, which has contributed to the view that external
66 tectonic or climatic perturbations are required to explain landscape transience in tectonically
67 quiescent settings (4, 9–12).

68 Drainage network reorganization is also important for understanding how hydrographic
69 barriers and connections influence continental biogeography. As the world's nutrient conveyor
70 belts and important biogeographical barriers, river networks and their dynamic reorganizations
71 were instrumental in building Earth's biodiversity (1, 2). A large body of work has linked river
72 reorganization to patterns of endemism, phylogeography, and diversification in both terrestrial
73 and aquatic taxa across multiple regions, including the Amazon lowlands (15, 20, 22, 24–29),
74 New Zealand (34–36), Africa (37, 38), Madagascar (39), Australia (40), Patagonia (41), the
75 Appalachian Mountains (42, 43), and the Ligurian Alps (44). However, the key unresolved issue
76 is not whether river capture can matter biologically, but how, where, and how often river captures
77 are initiated in tectonically stable landscapes.

78 This question is especially relevant in low-relief continent interiors, which are both
79 tectonically stable and disproportionately biodiverse (9, 15). Freshwater rivers host at least 26%
80 of all living vertebrate species based on freshwater fish alone, despite covering less than 0.01%
81 of the Earth's surface and routing less than 0.001% of the world's water budget (1, 2).
82 Biodiversity studies have therefore argued that the persistence of high lowland diversity requires
83 mechanisms capable of repeatedly displacing barriers to dispersal under long-term tectonic
84 stability (16, 19). Recurring drainage network reorganization via river capture may help address
85 this gap, but a systematic trigger has remained unclear.

86 Here we quantify an underexplored lithologic control on river network reorganization
87 through differential base-level perturbation across neighboring basins. This mechanism explains
88 how drainage reorganization can be initiated in areas far from lithologic transitions and across
89 multiple spatial scales. Using topographic analyses from landscapes in South and North America
90 together with numerical landscape-evolution models, we show that the style, timing, magnitude,
91 and spatial distribution of drainage reorganization depend on rock heterogeneity and contrasts in

92 erosional resistance. These findings provide a geomorphic framework for identifying where river
 93 captures are most likely to occur and for generating temporally and spatially explicit hypotheses
 94 about the co-evolution of landscapes and species.
 95

96
 97 **Figure 1: Transient topography upstream of hard rocks in the Guiana Shield and similar examples in South**
 98 **and North America (inset).** a) Eastern Guiana Shield in northern Pará, BR; b) Oblique view of the plateau-top
 99 landscape transients and shrinking basin. *Global Inset:* Additional study areas with the same characteristic
 100 topographic transience upstream of hard rocks (see Figs. S2-S9).

101
 102 **Results**

103 ***Widespread river reorganization in response lithologic perturbation***

104 Across diverse geologic and climatic contexts, exposed hard rock units consistently form
 105 distinct lithologic ridges, often characterized by numerous wind gaps (abandoned ridge-top
 106 fluvial valleys) and water gaps (rivers traversing hard rock ridges). In regions such as the Guiana
 107 Shield (N Brazil), the eastern Paraná Basin (SE Brazil), the Tavaputs Plateau (SW United States),

108 and San Rafael Swell (SW United States), the watersheds of subparallel neighboring rivers
109 crossing water gaps are at different average elevations upstream of the hard rocks (Fig. 1; Fig.
110 S1-S5). These macrogeomorphic features, characterized by short-wavelength variations in basin
111 average elevations, align with Gilbert's (1877) (3) proposition that a resistant bedrock in a river's
112 course can impede its downcutting relative to a more powerful neighboring stream (or one that
113 does not flow over the same resistant rock (4–6)). Thus, before diving into the analysis of the
114 study areas, we explore this scenario using numerical landscape evolution models based on the
115 stream power incision law (see Methods). These models simulate the exhumation of a resistant
116 rock at the lower end of semi-parallel basins sharing the same base-level. The setup includes a
117 low and constant background rock uplift rate (1–100 m/My), consistent with tectonically
118 quiescent regions.

119 As the modeled hard rock is exhumed, it outcrops at the beds of rivers with contrasting
120 incision power, inducing differential base-level perturbations along the strike of the outcropping
121 hard rock. The differential incision power of each river at the to-be-formed water-gap depends on
122 their relative drainage area; rivers with small basins upstream of the water-gap get perched
123 higher than their larger neighbors, generating a topographic step between adjacent basins (Fig. 2,
124 S14). This topographic step initiates in-situ inter-tributary drainage divide asymmetry, triggering
125 divide migration (Fig. 2). Because the base-level perturbation at the water-gap propagates
126 upstream, drainage reorganization dynamics ensue tens of kilometers away from the lithologic
127 contact, where there is no across-divide rock contrast (Fig. 2, S14, S15). Over time, the
128 differential cross-divide relief (ΔH) along the main drainage divides increases as larger basins
129 consume smaller ones (Fig. S16, S17), accelerating area transfer. This positive feedback
130 continues until the expanding basins completely consume the shrinking drainage basins (Fig. 2).

131 During transience, the small basins shrink from every direction, with their headwaters
132 furthest away from the lithologic contact serving as the fastest and leading edge of drainage area
133 loss and river captures, often corresponding with a triple-drainage divide (Supporting Video S1).
134 Lastly, wind-gaps systematically form along main drainage divides and along the modeled hard
135 rock where small basins shrunk completely, forming paleo-water gaps (Fig. S15). In all cases
136 with full basin shrinkage, the final river network reorganization is via a large river capture of the
137 trunk stream, thus cutting off the water gap (Fig. 2; Supporting Video S1).

138

139 **Figure 2: Numerical landscape evolution model showing systematic drainage network reorganization in**
140 **response to the exhumation of a resistant lithology.** As the hard rock exhumes, larger drainage basins equilibrate
141 at lower elevations and gain area from the smaller, perched basins. Note that the process affects the headwater
142 region away from the lithologic contact and continues via divide migration and large river captures from all
143 directions and at the leading edge of basin shrinkage (#6 and #7) progressively closer to the lithologic contact
144 (Supporting Video 1). River network is shown in black. The river network in the shrinking basin is highlighted in
145 orange.

146

147 ***Diagnosing lithologic controls of ongoing landscape transience***

148 The macrogeomorphologic patterns and systematic topographic transients (i.e. divide
149 asymmetries, river captures, wind and water gaps) revealed by the numerical models (Fig. 2; Fig.
150 S14, S15; Supporting Video 1) can be observed in the study areas (Fig. 1; Fig. S1-S5).
151 Topographic profiles along and across these study areas reveal a repeated, short-wavelength
152 pattern of perched basins (Fig. S6-S9) with systematic across-divide relief asymmetries that
153 indicate some of these basins are actively shrinking in all directions (Fig. 1; Fig. S10-S13).
154 Importantly, these patterns extend from the main lithologic transition up to the basins'
155 headwaters (i.e., far from the ridge-forming rock contact) (Fig. 1b; S6-S9). All study areas reveal
156 a topographic step near the headwaters of shrinking basins coinciding with a triple-drainage
157 divide (Fig. S6-S9). Here, river captures between the parallel drainage basins are detected in
158 map-view and through river profiles in the study areas (Fig. 1a; S6-S9), also consistent with the
159 models (Fig. S15). The consistency of these geomorphic features upstream of hard rocks across
160 tropical and desert landscapes and the high similarity with the numerical models suggests they
161 share the same underlying mechanism of lithologic regulation of base level and river
162 reorganizations.

163 Though the similarity of geomorphic signals between real and modeled landscapes is
164 encouraging, we have only qualitatively linked them to the lithologic perturbation. To do so
165 quantitatively, we resort again to our numerical models to devise a diagnosing framework. In the
166 numerical models, the imposed background rock uplift rate is uniform across all parallel-flowing
167 simulated basins. Therefore, we can use a lithologically-corrected proxy that predicts the rivers'
168 steady-state elevation (χ' , see Methods) immediately upstream of the lithologic transition (Fig.
169 3). This proxy can be compared between rivers crossing the hard rock and yield a $\Delta\chi'$ metric that
170 captures the differential equilibrium elevation at the rock contact for neighboring basins.
171 Importantly, $\Delta\chi'$ forms a linear relationship with the average cross-divide asymmetries (ΔH) of
172 the main divides separating the semi-parallel basins (Fig. 3a, b; Fig. S17; see Methods and
173 Supporting Video 2), thus scaling with divide migration rates (7). This relationship remains
174 consistent for continuous drainage area transfer via divide migration, and its slope is dependent
175 on the river concavity index (Fig. S17; Table S3). Deviations of the relationship can result from a
176 coincidence of asymmetric divides with local lithologic contrasts (Fig. S17) or large river

177 captures. The latter, disturbs this relationship due to discrete drainage area transfer faster than the
 178 adjustment of across-divide relief (Fig. 3b, Fig. S18).

179 Using this framework and assuming uniform uplift across neighboring basins, we
 180 quantified the $\Delta H - \Delta\chi'$ relationships in the study areas. These relationships align with the trends
 181 predicted by the numerical models (Fig. 3a, b). In the Guiana Shield, drainage divides separating
 182 basins affected by large river captures (8) deviate from the main trend, forming a characteristic
 183 Z-shape pattern consistent with model predictions (Fig. 3b, c; Fig. S18; Supporting Video 3). In
 184 the Eastern Paraná basin and Tavaputs Plateau, the $\Delta H - \Delta\chi'$ relationships adhere to the
 185 concavity-dependent trends determined by the numerical models (Fig. 3d, e). The San Rafael
 186 Swell also follows the concavity-dependent trend albeit with scattered $\Delta\chi'$ potentially owing to
 187 the complex rock exposure patterns (Fig. 3f, Fig. S8, S9) (9, 10). From these analyses, we
 188 conclude that the spatial patterns of divide asymmetries and river captures observed in the study
 189 areas reveal ongoing drainage network reorganizations triggered by lithologic perturbations of
 190 base-level tens to hundreds of kilometers away from the migrating divides (Fig. 1; Fig. S1-S9),
 191 supporting Gilbert's (1877) mechanistic hypothesis (3).

192
 193 **Figure 3: Lithology-corrected χ' predicts drainage divide asymmetry in models and empirical landscapes. a)**
 194 **Conceptual model exemplifying the drainage network response to the exhumation of hard rocks and the divides**
 195 **affected. b) Left: Conceptual delta-plots for migrating drainage divides regulated by lithology. Right: Conceptual**
 196 **graph showing how large river captures disturb the main divide migration trend; c-f) $\Delta H - \Delta\chi'$ for the study areas as**

197 labeled ($\Delta\chi$ computed using empirically determined concavity indexes, Fig. S19-S22) and the concavity-dependent
 198 trends (gray line) determined from numerical models (Supporting Information).

199

200 **Onset of divide migration, area-loss positive feedback, and river captures**

201 Motivated by the agreement between model and empirical observations, we explore how
 202 lithologic heterogeneity influences the timescales and magnitudes of drainage area transfer, as
 203 well as the partitioning between divide migration and river captures. The spatial extent and
 204 erodibility contrast of the exhumed rock controls the rates of basin shrinkage and divide
 205 migration (Fig. 4). The time required for the shrinking basin in Fig. 2 (orange rivers) to be fully
 206 consumed decreases nonlinearly with decreasing erodibility and increasing outcrop width of the
 207 resistant lithology (Fig. 4a, b).

208 Full shrinkage of basins ensues due to the positive area-loss feedback and continue for
 209 10^6 to 10^8 model years, consistent with previous theoretical predictions (11). Each area-loss
 210 event triggers a commensurate acceleration of drainage divide migration rates (Fig. 4c; Fig. S16,
 211 S17). This acceleration is also dependent on the degree of lithologic perturbation, such as
 212 outcrop widths (Fig. 4c), but independent of the background uplift rate (Fig. 4d), consistent with
 213 previous studies (12).

214

215 Figure 4: **Divide migration and river capture dynamics from numerical model experiments.** **a)** Basin-shrinkage
216 times for changes in outcrop width for the first basin to shrink (see Fig. 2); **b)** Basin-shrinkage times for changes in
217 the erodibility contrast between the hard rock unit and the background erodibility; **c)** Divide migration rates over
218 time highlighting the effect of outcrop width on response times of the shrinking basin (c.f. Panel **a**) and mean divide
219 migration rates (dots) and averaged trends (solid lines); **d)** Similar response time and divide migration rates for fixed
220 outcrop width and erodibility contrast but with variable uplift rates for $n = 1$. Results focus on the first 50 My of
221 model run during which the first basin shrinks to completion (c.f. Fig. 2). These results are obtained from a basin in
222 the center of the model and are not influenced by model edge effects.

223

224 The exhumation of a hard rock also influences the spatial distribution of river captures
225 (Fig. 5). As the leading edge of basin-shrinkage moves towards the lithologic contact (Fig. 2), it
226 leaves a gradient in river capture ages, with ages progressively younger towards the rock contact
227 (N-S direction in the models) (Fig. 5). As multiple basins shrink over 200 My of model time, the
228 model produces a mosaic of river captures with different sizes and ages (Fig. 5). This spatial
229 pattern suggests that the large river captures on the edge of the Guiana Shield (Fig. 1) and other
230 study areas (Fig. S6-S9) could have progressed in a similar manner.

231 The spatial and erodibility variations of rock types control the frequency-magnitudes of
232 river captures (Fig. 6a-f). Large river captures are more likely and more frequent in models with
233 rock resistance contrasts (Fig. 6a) and greater outcrop extent (Fig. 6b) despite similar response
234 times (Fig. 4a, b) and divide migration rates (Fig. 4c). The timescales of river capture events
235 range from 10^5 y for the smallest to 10^7 y for the largest captures (Fig. 6c, d). As the lithologic
236 perturbation increases (i.e. larger contrast or wider outcrops), the recurrence times decrease
237 nonlinearly with increasing river capture magnitude (Fig. 6c, d), from 1.3x faster for headwater
238 river captures to >100x faster for captures involving trunk streams. Consequently, we observe
239 positive relationships between the largest river capture event in the models and the hard rock's
240 erodibility contrasts (Fig. 6e) and outcrop extent (Fig. 6f). These patterns arise as harder rocks
241 increasingly reroute river networks via river captures rather than gradual divide migration (Fig.
242 7a, b). The fraction of total area loss accounted by river captures fluctuate over time and is
243 dependent on the lithologic contrasts and outcrop widths (Fig. 7c, d), despite similar response
244 times (Fig. 4a,b). We conclude that river captures frequency-magnitudes are more sensitive to
245 lithologic complexities while divide migration rates fluctuate within the same ranges for the
246 same perturbations, only differing on the timing of those fluctuations.

247
 248 Figure 5: **Systematic spatiotemporal distribution of river captures.** River capture map (basins captured by
 249 headwater streams colored by model time) shown with the drainage network after 200 My.
 250

251
 252 Figure 6: **The lithologic control of river captures.** **a, b** Cumulative area transferred via river captures for varying
 253 contrasts between K_{low} and K_{high} and for models with varying outcrop extent (i.e. extent of K_{low} in Fig. 4). **c, d**
 254 Recurrence interval of river captures for a subset of the models shown in panels **a** and **b**, respectively; **e-f** Largest
 255 river capture for the first basin to shrink for the erodibility contrast experiments (**d**) and the outcrop width (**d**). We
 256 restricted the analysis to a basin in the middle of the model to not be biased by edge basins, which only shrink on
 257 one side. Results for a model uplift rate of 40 m/My and m/n of 0.45.

258

259 Figure 7: **Partitioning of drainage area transfer between divide migration and river capture.** The figure reveals
 260 that river captures gain importance as a mechanism of drainage area transfer and drainage network reorganization as
 261 the contrast in rock resistance to erosion increases. Because response times are similar (Fig. 4a, b), rock strength
 262 controls the mode of drainage network reorganization in addition to the pace.

263

264 Discussion

265 *Implications for landscape evolution in continent interiors*

266 Though markedly different in geologic (8, 13–17) and climatic histories, the study areas reveal
 267 systematic landscape transience trends that align closely with the lithologically perturbed model
 268 landscapes (Fig. 3, S6-S9). The models also predict divide migration rates that reach 1-2 mm/yr

269 when nearing the complete shrinkage of a drainage basin despite low uplift rates (Fig. 4c, d).
270 Though model-dependent, these rates are consistent with global observations of divide migration
271 rates in tectonically quiescent settings (18). The accompanying numerous river captures cause
272 short-lived pulses of erosion and sediment flux consistent with sedimentary records offshore the
273 tectonically quiescent eastern North America (19) (e.g. $1\text{-}5 \times 10^3 \text{ km}^3/\text{My}$, Fig. S23, Supporting
274 Video 5). These findings suggest that fluctuations in sediment fluxes in passive margins may
275 contain records of river capture events (20).

276 The tectonically quiescent areas studied here are characterized by long-term uplift and
277 erosion rates generally below 100 m/My. External perturbations, such as mantle-driven uplifts in
278 rigid lithospheric settings like the Guiana Shield, cannot explain the observed systematic short-
279 wavelength divide asymmetries between basins as small as 100 km^2 . While transient flexural
280 forcings of cold lithosphere could still create surface uplift/subsidence gradients at the spatial
281 scale of the lithologic outcrops tested here (21), these gradients would have to vary 5-fold or
282 more (i.e. from 10 - 20 m/My to 50 - 100 m/My) across a 10-50 km wide zone to account for the
283 same effects demonstrated in this study using 5-fold (or more) contrasts in lithology. Such short-
284 wavelength variations in uplift and erosion rates are not consistent with observations in continent
285 interiors nor the changes in uplift rates driven by time-varying elastic thickness of the lithosphere
286 (21, 22). Conversely, the erodibility of the most common rock types varies over many orders of
287 magnitude (23), thus capable of creating the disturbances described here.

288 The perched low-relief basins and surfaces in our models form due to an initial upstream
289 propagating low-erosion wave and the progressive drainage area loss (Supporting Video 01).
290 These counter-intuitive results suggest that the formation of vast plains can result from low-
291 erosion pulses triggered by heterogeneous lithology near baselevel. This conclusion is contrary to
292 conventional models attributing leveled surfaces to either post-uplift topographic lowering
293 through decaying topography, cyclical erosive waves, or pulses of uplift and erosion (24–26).
294 Our results offer the simpler and compelling alternative interpretation of a protracted history of
295 exhumation of various rock types driving growth and decay of low-relief surfaces by positive
296 area-loss feedback that is independent of turning uplift or climatic changes “on and off”.

297 Importantly, these results imply that (i) plateaus can form *in-situ* as hard rocks raise the
298 baselevel; (ii) the relief between plateaus and lowlands can grow over time as plateaus shrink
299 depending on flexural isostasy controls (13); (iii) persisting water gaps are sustained by drainage

300 network dynamics upstream of lithologic contacts while shrinking basins transform water gaps
301 into wind gaps along the resistant rock ridge. These findings not only reveal how tectonic
302 quiescence and lithologic variability fuel river captures, but also how they can create elevated
303 low-relief landscapes which are known for hosting endemic species (27, 28).

304 The simple end-member scenarios tested here in which a single hard rock is used as the
305 trigger suggest that greater diversity of rocks such as those observed in cratons and highly
306 stratified settings (i.e. Fig. S2-S5) could boost drainage reorganization. However, high lithologic
307 complexity has also been shown to cancel out prior perturbations (29). Thus, we posit that the
308 typical lithologic complexity of intraplate settings can create a non-unique spatiotemporal
309 spectrum of river capture rates and ages. Collectively, our models help explain erosive patterns
310 and river network reorganizations in continent interiors independently of climate or tectonics and
311 highlight how hard rocks may be the first-order regulators of drainage reorganizations, landscape
312 evolution, and geometric disequilibrium of river basins observed in continent interiors (30).

313

314 ***Why are river captures a staple of tectonically quiescent regions?***

315 In tectonically active regions, rivers steepen in response to drainage area loss and equalize
316 erosion rates across the divides, thus preventing the positive area-loss feedback (12). Conversely,
317 the low-uplift conditions modeled here favor the positive area-loss feedback due to lithologic
318 heterogeneity and long response times. For higher uplift rates, the shrinking basins adjust to the
319 degree of base level perturbation in time to equilibrate erosion rates across drainage divides,
320 halting the basin shrinkage and sustaining more water gaps. For example, while a 5-km-wide
321 exposure of hard rock drives positive area-loss feedback in models with 20 m/My background
322 uplift, it does not trigger it in a model with 40 m/My background uplift. It is necessary to
323 increase the lithologic perturbation to continue to drive the positive area-loss feedback for higher
324 uplift rates (Supporting Video 4). Thus, the lower the background uplift, the more susceptible a
325 landscape is to the lithologic control of base level demonstrated here. Consistently, increases in
326 background uplift rates beyond 100 m/My promote the decrease in the sizes of river captures
327 (Fig. S24).

328

329 ***Implications for biogeography***

330 Lowland biodiversity occurs in complex mosaics of richness and endemism influenced by the
331 spatial organization of hydrographic basins (31–35). Our results reconcile the conundrum of
332 high species richness in slowly eroding and supposedly geomorphologically stable continent
333 interiors (34, 36). Several case studies have demonstrated the influence of past drainage network
334 reorganizations on the taxonomic and genetic diversity of terrestrial and aquatic organisms (34,
335 37). The exhumation of hard rocks provides a protracted mechanism for recurring river capture
336 events and reconfiguration of hydrographic basins, all regulated by the spatial distribution and
337 diversity of rock types on the surface. This mechanism can lead to geologically-dependent rates
338 of change in connectivity that simultaneously promote vicariance and dispersal of terrestrial and
339 aquatic organisms. This mechanism may thus fill important gaps in our understanding of the co-
340 evolution of drainage networks and biodiversity. For example, the large lowland rivers in the
341 Amazon are dispersal barriers for terrestrial species and connectivity corridors for aquatic
342 species (Ribas et al. 2025, Albert et al. 2018). Phylogenomic analyses reveal, in some cases, a
343 time frame of diversification that is consistent with independent evidence of timing of river
344 reorganizations (Hoorn et al. 2010, Albert et al. 2018), but in other cases the origins and
345 diversification of species with distributions currently bounded by Amazonian rivers are
346 consistently younger than the major drainage reorganizations (34, 36, 38, 39).

347 The Amazon region, the most biodiverse lowland landscape on Earth, provides an ideal
348 scenario to further discuss the implications of our river reorganization mechanism for biotic
349 diversification. For the biota with dispersal restricted by large river channels, a river capture
350 promotes both the isolation of populations previously connected as well as contact among
351 populations previously isolated (Fig. 8). Isolation of terrestrial populations and species by river
352 channels are described for many Amazonian birds and primates (28, 34, 38–40). Recent ages of
353 origin for species isolated by large rivers in old geological terrains, like the Brazilian shield, are
354 consistent with barrier displacement causing isolation upstream of the sedimentary-basement
355 lithological transitions south of the Amazon River (34, 35). For aquatic species, a river capture
356 results in community wide merging among adjacent river basins and isolation of the shrinking
357 basin post-capture. With the ongoing drainage evolution and runaway shrinkage of vulnerable
358 basins, the isolated downstream drainage might be critically reduced causing extinction of the
359 isolated population (fish example in Fig. 8), increasing extinction rates as expected (41) and
360 observed in the Amazon (33).

361 When a river capture leads to a barrier displacement, the removal of dispersal limitation
362 leads to contact among populations previously isolated. This process, in turn, may have two
363 distinct outcomes. If the taxa that come into contact already have reproductive isolation, they
364 may coexist, increasing local species richness (fish example in Fig. 8) or competitive exclusion
365 may eliminate one of them over time. Species composition of fish communities in Amazonia
366 shows non monophyletic species assemblages in subbasins and many species with distributions
367 spanning distinct, adjacent subbasins (42, 43) suggesting that merging of aquatic biotas due to
368 river capture has been an important mechanism for the assemblage of the current communities.
369 Alternatively, if the taxa involved come into contact and hybridize (primate example in Fig. 8),
370 complex genomic outcomes are possible, including differential genomic introgression (38, 44,
371 45) and even hybrid speciation (46).

372 Overall, there is a consensus in phylogeography studies that river reorganizations
373 contribute to regulate the net diversification of biotas, generating complex patterns of local
374 species richness, endemism, and spatial turnover (33, 47, 48). Exploring how the complex,
375 geologically regulated timescales and spatiotemporal gradients of river captures and basin
376 shrinkage compare to the timescales of population genomic divergence and speciation needs
377 deeper investigation, with the geological processes described here forming a mechanistic
378 baseline for the interpretations.

379

380

381 Figure 8: **Hypothetical scenarios depicting the consequences of river capture for terrestrial and aquatic**
382 **organisms.** (a) Species distributions before the capture event; (b) Phylogenetic relationships of species before the
383 capture event; (c) Connectivity changes triggered by the capture event. Capture causes both isolation and contact
384 among populations. Isolation may cause persistence of two distinct taxa (monkey example) or extinction of a range
385 restricted taxon (fish example). Contact may cause introgression (monkey example) or co-occurrence (fish
386 example). (d) Phylogenetic relationships of taxa after the capture event.

387

388 *Timescales of river capture and macroevolution*

389 Although prolonged time for species accumulation is often posited as the underlying
390 condition of highly diverse lowland biomes (49), biogeographic and macroevolutionary studies
391 show that diversification rates fluctuated over geologic time (33). Consequently, explaining the
392 unparalleled and complex distribution of biodiversity of these continental ecosystems requires
393 numerous vicariant and dispersal events over timescales longer than ca. 100 ky Pleistocene
394 climatic oscillations (31, 33, 50, 51). For example, the timescales of diversification recorded in
395 the genomes of birds and primates in the Amazon region range from 10^5 to nearly 10^7 years (Fig.
396 9), similar to the timescales of river captures produced by our numerical modeling experiments
397 (Fig. 6). Furthermore, our results suggest that these timescales vary depending on the size of the
398 river capture event, with larger ones being less frequent (Fig. 6c, 7b). This variability in
399 frequency-magnitude distribution adds complexity to deciphering the trajectories going from
400 population isolation to the origin of reproductively isolated species.

401 Population genomic studies in highly biodiverse tropical lowlands indicate that there is a
402 continuum between population fragmentation generating genetic structure and the origin of
403 stable reproductively isolated species. While population structure spatially delimited by the
404 current positions of large rivers occurs at time scales of 70 to 700 thousand years (38), the
405 establishment of reproductive isolation may require longer isolation, estimated at about one
406 million years for one genus of Amazonian birds (52). The timing for speciation also depends on
407 intrinsic characteristics of each taxon, genomic architecture (53), and selection pressures (54,
408 55). According to available phylogeographic studies, most currently recognized Amazonian bird
409 and primate species originated between 0.5 and 3 million years ago (34), but in Amazonian
410 primates there is evidence of phenotypically stable and diagnosable species with distributions
411 delimited by rivers that originated in last 3 to 5 hundred thousand years (56).

412 While bearing in mind that timescales of numerical models are not exactly equivalent to
413 real timescales and depend on their parameterization, the most frequent, small river captures that
414 lead to basin shrinkage would reintegrate species previously separated by an earlier river capture,
415 promoting momentary population isolation, but not speciation. Taking from the empirical
416 examples of the Amazon, these higher-frequency, piecemeal events may be preserved in
417 genomes but may not necessarily be linked to higher species diversity. If our models represented
418 the reality, it would take the larger, 10^6 year river captures of trunk streams linked to
419 intermediate/advanced stages of basin shrinkage to promote reproductive isolation and increase
420 local taxonomic diversity. Borrowing from macroecological principles and comparing our model
421 timescales to the terrestrial species lineages in the Amazon, our results align with the
422 requirement that river captures need to be rare enough to allow for isolation and speciation to
423 occur (41), but frequent enough to influence diversification rates in the scale of several hundred
424 to a couple of million years. Understanding which lithologic configurations produce these
425 optimal timescales and which species are sensitive to them may help constrain continental
426 phylogeography. It may also contribute to some ongoing contentious debates involving the co-
427 evolution of landscapes and biodiversity, like the large-scale reorganization of the Amazon
428 drainage in the Miocene versus the younger age of multiple taxa with distributions delimited by
429 Amazonian rivers (36). However, detailed mechanistic approaches will require whole-landscape
430 multidisciplinary efforts.

431 In conclusion, the lithologic regulation of landscape dynamics shown here suggests river
432 captures are repeatable in geologic time, need no change in external forcings (but can be
433 enhanced or dampened by them) and are compatible with the timescales and mosaiced
434 distribution of species richness and endemism across highly biodiverse regions, such as South
435 America (31, 33). External forcings of biodiversity such as geodynamic, tectonic, or climatically
436 induced landscape dynamics (1, 50, 57) require on/off histories of multiple events that cannot
437 fully explain hundreds of recurring intraplate vicariant and dispersal events (33). Guaranteed by
438 the heterogeneity of the continental crust, the changing rock tapestry over geologic time has
439 likely accompanied a rich history of river capture events that affected population connectivity
440 simultaneous to nutrient-yielding erosive pulses (1, 2), both conditions leading to high
441 diversification rates (47, 51, 58, 59). As basin expansion/shrinkage and substrate heterogeneity

442 influence the diversity of ecological habitats (1, 60, 61), these results provide a testable pathway
443 to mechanistically link rock diversity and biodiversity

444
445 **Figure 9: Published estimates of lineage-split ages for Amazonian birds and primates whose present-day**
446 **distributions are associated with major river barriers.** The histogram is shown to compare the order of
447 magnitude of biological divergence times with the timescales of river capture produced by the numerical
448 experiments. This comparison is intended to assess temporal plausibility and does not constitute a direct biological
449 test of the geomorphic mechanism proposed here. Data from Ribas et al (2025)(34).

450 **Methods**

451 *Modeling Landscape Evolution*

452 We use the Landlab library to model landscape evolution (62, 63). Landscape change is modeled
453 as a continuity equation where elevation is the balance between an imposed background uplift
454 rate (U) and erosion rate (E). Erosion rate is computed as the sum of fluvial (the stream power
455 incision model) and hillslope erosion (linear hillslope diffusion):

456
457
$$\frac{dz}{dt} = U - E = U - [K A^m S^n + D \nabla z] \quad (1),$$

458
459 where U is uplift (m/y), E erosion (m/y), K the erodibility coefficient (m^{1-2m}/y), A drainage area
460 (m^2), S river channel slope (m/m), and m and n are nondimensional exponents that are related to
461 erosion process amongst other hydrologic properties (64), D is hillslope diffusivity (m^2/y), and
462 ∇z is hillslope gradient (m/m). The stream power is implemented with the fastscape algorithm
463 (65). To maintain the drainage network hydrologically connected throughout model runs, we use
464 Landlab's *DepressionFinder* to force flow routing through local pits in the landscape.
465 Contrasting rock types are exhumed using the Lithology component(66).

466
467 *Model limitations*

468 The map-view configuration of the lithologic contacts here are a simplification of real
469 landscapes. While we impose a hard rock that is perpendicular to the main flow of river
470 networks, this condition is not always the case in nature. We highlight that as long as rivers cross
471 over hard rocks in the downstream direction, the effects shown here will still ensue. Thus, the
472 configuration we chose does not mean that real landscapes need to follow the same
473 configuration.

474 The chosen lithologic boundary condition simulates the simplest scenario of an exhuming
475 hard rock with vertical edges (i.e. 90° contact). As the contact angles decrease to sub-horizontal,
476 the outcropping extent of the hard rock changes and migrates according to the exhumation rate.
477 While we do not explore the effects of dip angles in this study, the drainage reorganization
478 dynamics would still ensue due to the exhumation of the hard layer (67). Depending on the
479 thickness and polarity of the dipping layer (i.e. opposite or parallel to river flow), the migration

480 of the rock contact would, respectively, speed up or slow down the transient signals highlighted
481 here (67).

482 The models shown here do not incorporate isostatic compensation. However, we expect
483 that flexural isostasy would exacerbate the effects shown here due to the creation of spatial
484 gradients in rock uplift rate in response to differential erosion and river captures (21, 68) which
485 could mask the first-order lithologic effects shown here. Incorporating flexural isostasy requires
486 knowledge of elastic thickness (21) and would be a form of tailoring the investigation to different
487 geologic settings and introducing variability in the observed lithologic control of river captures.

488

489 *A lithologically-constrained proxy for steady-state channel elevation*

490 The steady state integral solution (69) of Equation 1 yields the linear relationship between
491 elevation and χ used in χ plots such as those in Fig. 3:

492

$$493 \quad z(x) = z_b + \left(\frac{U}{KA_0^m}\right)^{1/n} \chi, \text{ where } \chi = \int_{x_b}^x \left(\frac{A_0}{A(x)}\right)^{m/n} dx, \quad (2),$$

494

495 where $z(x)$ is the elevation along a distance, x , upstream; x_b and z_b the base-level distance and
496 elevation, respectively, A_0 a constant typically set to 1. At steady state, the slope of the χ plot (i.e.
497 $[U/K]^{1/n}$) is river steepness (k_{sn}). Non-uniform U and K distributions can be incorporated to yield
498 the chi-prime (χ') coefficient(30):

$$499 \quad \chi' = \int_{x_b}^x \left(\frac{U(x)}{K(x)} \frac{A_0^m}{A(x)^m}\right)^{\frac{1}{n}} dx = \int_{x_b}^x k_{sn}(x) \left(\frac{A_0}{A(x)}\right)^{m/n} dx \quad (3),$$

500

501 Because $k_{sn} = (U/K)^{1/n}$ in the stream power model, k_{sn} patterns can safely be interpreted as
502 reflecting variations in rock erodibility in intraplate settings (70) and used to compute χ' .

503 Because rivers are linked to the same base-level downstream of the rock transition, this
504 proxy captures the differential base-level perturbations caused by contrasts in rock erodibility
505 and outcrop extent. Using the regular χ method (i.e. Equation 2) can still predict the average
506 across-divide asymmetries when computed at the lithologic transition as we have computed here,
507 albeit with a slightly lower statistical significance (see Supporting Information, Fig. S25-S28).
508 We argue that using χ instead of χ' in areas with high contrasts in rock erodibility and/or flow

509 path over hard rocks as well as areas with incipient positive area-loss feedback will exacerbate
510 this discrepancy.

511

512 *Constructing a lithologically-constrained χ' grid*

513 Assuming that the term $(U/K)^{1/n}$ of Equation 2 is well approximated by k_{sn} , we construct a k_{sn}
514 map using the Topographic Analysis Kit (71) using the best-fit concavity index determined for
515 each study area (see below). To construct the χ' map, we first batch-compute k_{sn} , average this
516 grid in a window with a radius shorter than the spatial variation in rock types (i.e. 5,000 m for the
517 Guiana Shield and eastern Paraná study areas, and 500 m for the San Rafael Swell and Tavaputs
518 Plateau). Second, we assign the average k_{sn} per lithology to the geologic map of the area. This
519 lithologically-constrained k_{sn} grid is then used to find the normalized steady-state elevation using
520 Equation 3 applied in TopoToolbox(72). The best-fit concavity (m/n) was determined via an
521 optimization method applied to maximize the linearity of χ -elevation profiles (*mnoptimvar*
522 *function*) in TopoToolbox (73). In each study area, we applied the optimization to all basins with
523 a drainage area between $5 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^2$ and 10^8 m^2 (see Supporting Information). The average m/n of
524 all basins in each study area was used as the concavity for computing the grid of river steepness
525 and χ' . Best-fit concavity histograms of each study area are provided in the Supporting
526 Information.

527

528 *Computing the average across-divide relief asymmetry*

529 We use TopoToolbox's DIVIDEobj (74) to extract the across-divide relief asymmetry of the main
530 drainage divide separating two basin pairs. We isolate the main divide between the basin pairs
531 and, for each divide node, we extract the relief between the divide and the nearest channel
532 headwater on opposing sides using the function *vertdistance2stream* (73) (Schwanghart and
533 Scherler, 2014). The pairs of divide-to-channel relief are then subtracted to compute the across-
534 divide relief asymmetry. The subtraction follows the same order as the subtraction of χ' values
535 (i.e. west basin minus east basin) such that the asymmetry is always computed in directional
536 order, i.e. from one edge of the study area to the other (e.g. west to east), pair by pair. Enforcing
537 this order is useful to demonstrate the directionality of divide asymmetry and gives rise to the
538 negative slope of the $\Delta\chi'$ plot (Fig. 2). Based on the along-divide population of asymmetries
539 (ΔH), we take the bootstrapped mean of the entire drainage divide (see Supporting Information)

540 to be correlated with the $\Delta\chi'$. Taking the absolute value of these across-divide differences reveals
541 the positive relationship between ΔH and $\Delta\chi'$.

542 In the Guiana Shield and eastern Paraná basin study areas, a channel headwater is
543 determined as a cell with a 10^6 m² drainage area. In the San Rafael and Tavaputs Plateau study
544 areas, we use a 10^4 m² drainage area given the higher resolution of the dataset (i.e. USGS 10 m
545 DEM(75)) and following previous studies(9). Histograms of divide-to-channel head relief are
546 provided in the Supporting Information (Fig. S10-S13). These histograms showcase how the
547 main drainage divides are systematically asymmetric, highlighting the spatial significance of
548 divide mobility instead of local effects.

549

550 *Detecting river captures and divide migration and their timescales*

551 In the numerical models, we track river reorganization every 2 timesteps (i.e. 2 ky; a timestep is
552 1,000 years). Every 2 timesteps, numerical grids are sent to Matlab functions that use
553 Topotoolbox to identify river captures across the main drainage divides between distinct drainage
554 basins. To identify a river capture, we compare the drainage area of two topographic grids one at
555 the current timestep and one at two timesteps back. We define a river capture as the area change
556 that is at least two times a critical area threshold typical for channel formation of 10^6 m².
557 Because our cells are 200 m x 200 m, we define this threshold as 50 cells (i.e. 2×10^6 m²). Pixels
558 that increased area by this amount or greater are flagged as the point of a river capture and their
559 upstream areas and ages are stored. Anything per-pixel area increase that is below this threshold
560 is flagged as a pixel experiencing divide migration. River captures or divide migration within the
561 same drainage basin are not mapped as these do not have major implications for biodiversity,
562 although we acknowledge that they are also part of the geomorphic response.

563 Individual river capture data are then stored and analyzed for recurrence intervals. To
564 compute recurrence intervals, we rank river captures by their size. Using their ages (i.e. the
565 forward time model time), we compute the recurrence interval, R, as $(A+1)/n$, where A is the
566 absolute age-range analyzed (50 Ma in this case), and n is the number of river capture
567 observations.

568

569

570 **Data Availability**

571 The topographic data used in this study can be downloaded from OpenTopography servers at
572 <https://opentopography.org>. Geologic maps from the Guiana Shield and Eastern Paraná basins
573 can be downloaded from the Brazilian Geological Survey at <https://geosgb.sgb.gov.br>. Geologic
574 maps for the Tavaputs Plateau and San Rafael Swell can be downloaded from the Utah
575 Geological Association at <https://utahgeology.org>. All data associated with the topographic
576 analysis of the study areas as well as the seed noise data used as input to the landscape evolution
577 simulations are available in the Zenodo repository linked to this publication
578 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13328316>. Also provided in the Zenodo repository are: a) Model
579 output topography in 100ky timesteps as .mat containing GRIDObj for Topography and the
580 Lithology grid (Kgrid); b) Topographic data of model outputs organized as basin average data
581 upstream of the hard rock for model BLU4c; c) Cumulative drainage area transfer per timestep
582 for all models tested in the study; d) GRIDObj data containing maps of river captures and divide
583 migration per 2 ky timestep for model BLU4c.

584

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589

590 **Author Contributions**

591 P.V. conceived the study and conducted the analyses. P.V. wrote the first draft which was
592 reviewed and edited by D.P. C.R. Revised and rewrote discussions about biogeography and
593 phylogeography implications, which were revised by P.V. and D.P.

594

595 **Competing interests**

596 The authors declare no competing interests.

597

598 **Additional Information**

599 **Supporting Information**

600 Supporting Files accompanying this manuscript available at

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602 **Correspondence and request for materials** should be addressed to Pedro Val

603

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